

A Simplified Equation to “IS SPACE-TIME THE INERTIA OF PRIOR ENERGY AND MASS?”

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In my previous experiment concerning the conversion of energy and matter, defined in kilograms, it was proposed that the space-time curvature's composition is directly proportionate to the distance light travels within time, by the Energy $J=kg \cdot m^2/s^2$, to its matter 'kg,' by distance 'S²'.

A more broader understanding is that space-time itself, is composed of displaced matter and energy, which is no-longer visually present to the observers perspective of time. Moreover, the time of which energy and matter are present from one distance to another, is what appears to create a space for new matter and energy to travel within that formed region of space-time.

The geometry of this equation is forth dimensional, and is here as follows: The equation of space-time which I have pieced together as:

$$S = C^3 \cdot T^3$$

Thus shows the speed of light constant “C³” which is cubed to represent all three spacial dimensions on the x,y,z axis, and the distance of time ‘T³.’

And by reverse form to later connect this equation:

$$T = \frac{S}{C^3}$$

This shows that time itself is formed by the speed of light constant by distance of ‘S’ in meters per second.

Thus we pair with A. Einstein's equation:

$$E = MC^2$$

Famously shown as Energy converting to Matter by the speed of light.

And by reverse form, we show the Matter to Energy correlation:

$$M = \frac{E}{C^2}$$

By piecing together the following four equations “S.T.E.M.,” I have simplified this four quadrant dimension of space-time, by matter & energy, to the following equation: Where E is denoted as Energy “ $J=kg*m^2/s^2$, time remains ‘ T^2 ,’ and Matter is denoted as unit ‘kg’ by distance $1/m$ representing ‘ S^2 ’

$$ET^2 = MS^{-2}$$

Where:

$S = 1/m$ (space-time curvature). And exponent “-2” represents the inverse-square,

$T^2 = s^2$ (seconds squared),

$E =$ (Joules) $kg*m^2 / s^2$, and

$M = kg$ (mass).

The exponent “-2” in S^{-2} represents the inverse length squared ($1/m^2$), which physically shows that the space-time curvature increases due to contributing mass, and contracts at regions proportional to T^2 ; this correlation has no difference in stating that energy is the rate at which mass occupies curvature. If the equation holds validity, I propose it can be used to predict the amount of energy flare rate, in a given black hole, for a chosen duration rate, e.g Sagittarius A, or M87*.